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PRAECTICE

POTENTIALS OF AGROECOLOGICAL PRACTICES IN EAST AFRICA WITH A FOCUS ON CIRCULAR WATER-ENERGY- NUTRIENT SYSTEMS

D2.2 – Mapping of Integrated Aqua-Agriculture in East Africa

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Abstract	The present task investigated Integrated Agriculture-Aquaculture (IAA), in Kenya, Uganda, and Tanzania with the aim to collect information on integration, production, opportunities, and challenges encountered by farmers in the three countries. A KOBO digital questionnaire was used for the study. The results show that, in the three countries, the majority of IAA systems are privately owned with tilapia being the most farmed fish species. Almost 75% of the farms produced livestock in addition to fish. The most significant challenges highlighted by the study are the poor quality of feed and seed, the access to the market, the access to efficient fish handling and storage facilities, the lack of skilled workers, the insufficient production units, the unpredictability of the market prices, and drought. To address these challenges, the sector must be supported by policies that enable capacity building, enhance access to credit and support the post-harvest handling and process.
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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

Integrated Agriculture-Aquaculture (IAA), which involves producing fish alongside other goods (animals and crops) under the same system, has been carried out at different scales in three African countries: Kenya, Uganda, and Tanzania. This food production method has the potential to improve food and nutrition security, particularly for smallholder farmers. This is because IAA systems are resource-efficient and promote diversity in production, resulting in more sustainable food production. A survey was carried out to identify the locations and types of IAA practices in Kenya, Uganda, and Tanzania. The primary goal was to document IAA practices, levels of integration, production, opportunities, and challenges encountered by farmers in the three countries.

The study used a KOBO digital questionnaire, which was administered by trained extension services throughout the three countries. In Kenya, approximately half of the farms were individually owned, followed by government, family, and private. In Uganda 95% of the farms surveyed were individually owned. In both Tanzania and Kenya, men constituted the majority of respondents (64% and 79%, respectively). Tanzania has the highest number of employees with 60, followed by Kenya with 46 per farm. Private organizations in both countries employed an average similar number of workers (14 in Kenya and 13 in Tanzania). Only six farms in Tanzania reported their monthly income, thus comparing farm types was not possible. The average monthly income for these farms was €156 (Average exchange rate August 2023), ranging from more than €360 for two farms (one community-based with 48 employees and one individual with 8 employees) to €36 for a faith-based and family-owned farm.

Tilapia was the most farmed species, accounting for nearly 98% of farms in Kenya and Uganda, as well as 90% in Tanzania. Catfish was the second most common aquacultured species, being grown on 33, 55, and 15% of farms in Kenya, Tanzania, and Uganda, respectively. In Kenya, 87% of farms grew crops, and 87% of farms grew vegetables. In Tanzania, 91% of farms planted vegetables, whereas 18% grew seaweed. In Uganda, 46% farmed crops and aquaculture products, with 44% cultivating vegetables and 2% growing rice. Almost 75% of the farms produced livestock or other animals in addition to their aquaculture species. In Kenya, livestock production was more frequent, with almost 75% of farms producing chickens and 62% producing cattle (with some farms producing both), compared to 27% for both species (chicken and cattle) in Tanzania and 22% and 34% in Uganda. While all farms included in the analysis practised some type of integrated aquaculture-agriculture (IAA), not all farms featured both crops and livestock/animals. In Kenya and Tanzania, growing all three types of products was the most popular approach, with 76% and 55% of farms, respectively. The next most common type of IAA in the three countries was aquaculture and crops. In Uganda, the most common form of IAA was the

integration of fish with livestock, followed by fish and crops; however, just 2% of Ugandan farms combined aquaculture, crops, and livestock.

The most significant challenge that farmers face in both countries is poor feed and seed quality, which was identified in 91% of Tanzanian farms and 81% of Kenyan farms. Market access was the second most prevalent concern in Kenya, followed by access to efficient fish handling and storage facilities in Tanzania (the third most critical issue in Kenya). The other significant issues between both countries were a need for more skilled labour, insufficient production units, limited extension services, unpredictable market prices, and drought. The results of the survey have revealed that IAA is practised in all the 3 East African countries with varied levels of integration, production and income. The challenges and opportunities are similar across the countries with little specific variations among the countries. To address these challenges and tap into the opportunities identified, it will be important to strengthen the sector through policies, capacity building, enhanced access to credit and mark and strong support for post-harvest handling and processing.

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ABBREVIATIONS AND ACRONYMS

IAA	Integrated Aqua-Agriculture
RAS	Recirculating Aquaculture System
TIMPs	Technologies Innovations and Management Practices
GDP	Gross Domestic Product
LIFDCs	Low-Income Food-Deficit Countries
FAO	Food and Agriculture Organization
KMFRI	Kenya Marine and Fisheries Institute
BSFL	Black soldier fly larvae
NARO	National Agricultural Research Organisation
FAO	Food Agriculture Organization of the United Nations
SSC	South-South Cooperation
NaCCRI	National Crop Resources Research Institute
NSPFS	Nigerian Special Programme for Food Security
MSU	Maseno University
DALF	Department of Agriculture, Livestock and Fisheries
ABT	AquaBioTech Group
SAT	Sustainable Agriculture Tanzania
GU	University of Gothenburg
UMU	Uganda Martyrs University

1 INTRODUCTION

The projected global population figures of 8.6, 9.8, and 11.2 billion for the years 2030, 2050, and 2100 starkly emphasize the critical necessity for the development of sustainable, high-yield food production systems. These systems must prioritize efficient water and nutrient utilization while minimizing the adverse ecological impacts that often accompany traditional practices^[1]. This compelling urgency aligns seamlessly with the second goal of the Sustainable Development Goals - Zero Hunger, which seeks to attain food sovereignty, enhance nutritional well-being, and drive forward viable agricultural approaches^[1].

In the face of an expanding global population, the role of agriculture in safeguarding food security is of ever-increasing importance. An unsettling reality reveals that agriculture claims approximately 69-70% of the annual global water withdrawals, with arid regions experiencing an even more alarming rate of up to 90%^[2]. These figures emphasize the necessity for a shift towards sustainable agricultural practices, given agriculture's role as both a contributor to and a target of water pollution^[2]. Thus, any meaningful endeavour towards water conservation must commence with the strengthening of irrigation techniques, strategically employing the "more crops per drop" intensification approach to bolster yields, particularly in regions with limited water resources.

In parallel, aquaculture, while playing a pivotal role in global food production, poses its own challenges by imposing strain on water resources through the accumulation of waste arising from fish excretions and unconsumed feed^[3]. An effective and sustainable response requires the integration of aquaculture with agriculture, effectively transforming aquaculture into a non-consumptive production sector that complements sustainable farming practices^[4]. In this context, the concept of Integrated Aqua-Agriculture systems (IAAS) emerges as a compelling solution, highlighting its potential to elevate farm productivity, enhance water quality in fishponds, and mitigate the environmental impact of nutrient-rich water discharge, water-related expenses and chemical fertilizer usage^[4]. It is for this reason that the PrAECTiCe project mapped IAA practices in Kenya, Uganda and Tanzania to document the integration method, species and challenges associated with these practices in the three countries and their potential to enhance food security.

1.1 WHAT IS INTEGRATED AQUA-AGRICULTURE?

Integrated Aqua-Agriculture (IAA), colloquially referred to as "more crop per drop," offers a strategic blueprint for optimizing water usage and augmenting crop yield^[4]. IAA stands as a testament to the

concept of sustainable intensification, aiming to maximize food output from a given land area and water resources without compromising ecological equilibrium^[5]. The core of IAA involves the integration of aquatic and terrestrial components, incorporating fish, fruits, vegetables, and livestock. Within this intricate interplay, waste from one element serves as nourishment for another, ultimately leading to reduced pollution^[6]. IAA holds the potential for elevated sustainability, profitability, productivity, and resource efficiency, harnessing the full potential of water, land, and labour^[6, 7]. By bolstering food production and mitigating the challenges of water scarcity, IAA harbours transformative potential^[6].

FIGURE 1. (A) POND-DIKE CROPPING AND (B) FISH-LIVESTOCK-AGRICULTURE INTEGRATION^[9].

Pond-based IAA, a significant subset of this integrated approach, places fish cultivation at its core, serving both sustenance and economic purposes. This framework not only offers environmental viability but also provides a model for water recycling and nutrient utilization^[8]. Within this intricate tapestry of sustainable agriculture, IAA emerges as a guiding light, illuminating a path towards fortified food security, judicious resource management and harmonious ecological equilibrium (Figure 1 – illustration on integration in the IAA framework^[9]). These IAA systems can be adapted to an array of operational scales, spanning from small-scale subsistence farming to larger, commercially driven endeavours.

While Integrated Aqua-Agriculture practices have been previously studied and documented across East Africa, an overview of these practices is needed. This deliverable will document the existence of IAA sites in East Africa, specifically Kenya, Uganda and Tanzania. A first overview of current IAA sites will shed light on activities in this field based on internet research but also on knowledge of consortium partners regarding networks that are active in the field. While navigating through their respective journeys, it becomes apparent that each nation has woven its own IAA tapestry, intertwined with unique adaptations and approaches—an eloquent manifestation of their diverse socio-economic, geographical and environmental tapestries.

1.2 INTEGRATED AQUA-AGRICULTURE IN EAST AFRICA

1.2.1 Kenya

In Kenya, fish and other agricultural foods play a multifaceted role in the food systems, generating income, and providing a critical source of essential micronutrients, particularly for women and infants^[10, 11, 12]. The country is classified as Low-Income Food-Deficit Countries (LIFDCs) and ranked 90th out of 125 qualifying countries on the 2023 Global Hunger Index thus classifying the country's situation as "serious"^[13]. Technologies and innovations that could increase food production may have the potential to keep up with the country's soaring demand for fish and other food products. Integrated Aqua-Agriculture (IAA) is in its early stages in Kenya, with fish being integrated with other agricultural activities such as poultry, rice farming, livestock, pig rearing, and vegetables^[14]. Despite being actively promoted, IAA is still a marginal farming system in the country due to complex socioeconomic, environmental, technical, and institutional factors^[15]. There is a quantitative knowledge gap regarding how IAA can improve the welfare of smallholders and why this type of farming system technology is still marginal in Kenya. As a result, the suitability of this technology for smallholder farmers is necessary. In addition, knowledge of suitability evaluations is critical for policymakers because it can help design appropriate policies in terms of adoption and sustainability.

Rice-Fish Integration

One notable IAA practice in Kenya involves the integration of rice cultivation with fish farming. Farmers in regions like Homa Bay and Kisumu Counties have combined fishponds with rice paddies. Fish waste acts as a natural fertilizer for rice, while rice fields serve as natural filters for fishponds, purifying the water and increasing production of both^[16].

Poultry-Aquaculture Integration

Kenyan farmers are also working on integrating poultry into aquaculture. This can be achieved by constructing chicken coops directly over or near the fishponds. In such cases, the droppings from chickens fertilize the fishponds, encouraging primary production. In return, water from the fishponds is used to irrigate crops, showcasing a multi-tiered IAA system that optimizes resource utilization. In some cases, the chicken manure is fermented or boiled, and the concentrates are extracted and then added to the fishponds. This reduces the water quality deteriorations associated with the direct addition of chicken droppings into the fishpond. This integration has been shown to boost aquaculture productivity while dividing the risks of monoculture production^[17].

Aquaponics Systems

Kenya has also embraced aquaponics, an IAA system where fish farming effluents are used for the cultivation of crop plants hydroponically. Nutrient-rich fish tank water is directed to hydroponic beds, where plants absorb the nutrients, thereby purifying the water that is returned to the fish tanks. The most common aquaponics techniques being practised are deep water, floating raft, grow bed and nutrient film techniques (NFT).

Community-Led Initiatives

Community-driven IAA initiatives have gained traction, especially in rural areas. These initiatives aim to empower local communities to manage and benefit from integrated systems, contributing to food security and income generation. Most of these community-led initiatives rely on smallholder production systems with varied levels of integration. They are characterised by low productivity and low levels of integration due to a lack of access to credit, training, and technical skills.

Challenges and Opportunities

While Kenya's IAA practices have shown promise, challenges such as limited access to technical knowledge, infrastructure, markets, and credit services persist. However, this does not negatively impact the promising opportunities for expansion and improvement of the IAA practices in the country. Government support through policies and capacity-building programs can play a pivotal role in scaling up IAA practices and enhancing their contribution to the Kenyan food production sector. Therefore, IAA not only enhances food production but also aligns with Kenya's commitment to sustainable development and climate resilience.

Kenya's IAA endeavours underscore the nation's commitment to sustainable agriculture and resource management. Through the integration of aquaculture and agriculture, Kenya is moving towards

increased food security, economic prosperity, and ecological balance and contributing to the broader goal of achieving a more resilient and sustainable agricultural landscape.

1.2.2 Uganda

The dominant fish species in Uganda’s aquaculture are Nile tilapia and African catfish^[18, 19] (Figure 2). Other species such as common carp (*Cyprinus carpio*) are also produced but on a smaller scale^[Error! Bookmark not defined.]. Nile tilapia is currently the most farmed culture species in the country, whose production has consistently remained above that of African catfish since 2016, with production in 2020 estimated at 37,488 tons for African catfish and 86,011 tons for Nile tilapia (Figure 2). The drive to enhance the aquaculture sector, combined with the diversification of aquaculture production systems, has resulted into an increased demand for quality fish seed and feed. There is great potential for aquaculture in Uganda since about 18% of the surface area of the country consists of lakes, rivers, and swamps, some of which are untapped for aquaculture.

FIGURE 2. TRENDS IN ANNUAL AQUACULTURE PRODUCTION (TONS) IN UGANDA (2000-2020). ADAPTED FROM EGESSA ET AL. (2022).

In Uganda, IAA practices have been implemented primarily in small-scale farming systems and are largely undocumented^[12]. IAA is widely practiced through two main types: crop-fish integration and crop-fish-livestock integration. In crop-fish integration, fish and crops are combined in a mutually beneficial system. Fish raised in ponds provide fertilizer for crops like vegetables, fruits, and grains. Crop-fish-livestock is prevalent in rural areas, where smallholder farmers keep livestock and fish together in small-scale systems. Animal manure from the livestock serves as a nutrient source for fertilizing fishponds, leading to enhanced fish growth and production, while also reducing manure waste on the farm, benefiting the environment. In addition, to offset the high cost of fish feed which can account for up to 70% of fish production costs, the black soldier fly larvae (BSFL) have been

experimentally included in fish feeds as substitutes for the expensive fishmeal by different farmers practicing IAA in Uganda.

Fish-rice integration

This system thrives due to the mutual benefit and symbiotic relationship between rice and fish. Rice and fish farming is the most prevalent extensive aquaculture-crop integration system in Uganda. This initiative has been supported by The Food Agriculture Organization of the United Nations (FAO), the Government of the Republic of Uganda and the Government of the People's Republic of China under the FAO-China-Uganda South-South Cooperation (SSC) project.

Aquaponics

Aquaponics in Uganda has been promoted by different intervening agencies such as Water Governance Institute (WGI) and the National Agricultural Research Organization (NARO). WGI has supported farmers in the districts of Hoima, Wakiso and Kampala. However, due to limited technical knowledge in the management of aquaponics, the yields from these systems have been low, and most of them have been neglected to the high cost of power. Additionally, NARO has set up an aquaponics demonstration unit at the National Crop Resources Research Institute (NaCCRI), working with farmers in Jinja to enhance adoption and to evaluate commercial aquaponics for improved nutrition and income in Uganda. Based on the type of grow-bed, nutrient film technique and media-based culture are the most common aquaponic systems in Uganda. Leafy greens such as varieties of lettuce and spinach are the most cultivated plant species in both systems (personnel observation).

FIGURE 3. NUTRIENT FILM TECHNIQUE BASED- AQUAPONICS ESTABLISHED BY A FARMER IN FORT PORTAL, UGANDA.

Polyculture Integration

In polyculture, farmers mix more than one species of fish in a culture unit. Common polycultures include tilapia and catfish or tilapia and the common carp. Farmers normally select polyculture species to maximize production space and increase fish output per unit area of the farm used. Polyculture of African catfish (*Clarias gariepinus*) and Nile tilapia (*Oreochromis niloticus*) is a common practice in Uganda, sometimes supplemented using other fish species. Several small-scale farmers have merged fish farming with crop cultivation, finding ways to capture and reuse nutrients and resources^[11]. In regions like Jinja and Mukono, fishpond water is judiciously channeled to irrigate crops, fortify soil fertility and augment crop yields.

Seasonal Floodplain and Wetland Integration

Uganda's diverse topography has facilitated the integration of seasonal floodplains and wetlands with aquaculture. In areas like the Kabarole and Butaleja Districts, seasonal flooding is harnessed to create temporary fishponds within rice fields. The practice of rice-fish farming, not only boosts fish production but also capitalizes on the seasonal water dynamics^[20].

Community-Led Initiatives

Across Uganda, grassroots-level initiatives have thrived, empowering local communities to embrace IAA. These initiatives, often spearheaded by farmer cooperatives, underscore the power of community engagement and knowledge sharing in propelling the adoption and success of IAA practices.

Challenges and Opportunities

While Uganda's IAA practices hold immense promise, challenges such as limited access to good quality seed and feed, expensive feed, capital, technical expertise, and lack of niche market for aquaculture products persist. The developing integrated aqua-agriculture landscape presents exciting opportunities for collaboration between government agencies, research institutions and local communities to address these challenges using a multi-faceted approach, including capacity-building programs, policy support and market linkages.

Uganda's interest in integrated aqua-agriculture represents a beacon of innovation and adaptability. By seamlessly intertwining aquatic and agricultural realms, Uganda is not only augmenting its food production capabilities but also nurturing a sustainable paradigm that resonates with its rich natural heritage. As IAA practices continue to evolve, Uganda's journey serves as an inspiration, illustrating the potential of harmonizing diverse ecosystems to ensure food security, economic growth and environmental stewardship.

1.2.3 Tanzania

IAA approach has been found to help small scale farmers to become more resilient to climate change, provide a design that can operate in more remote areas, enhance poor farmers' livelihoods, have shown positive environmental impact and have often a positive social impact through enhanced food security, water availability and income source diversification and therefore has been proposed to be part of Tanzania's future aquaculture portfolio, to assure an aquaculture development that contributes to both economic growth, social justices and environmental qualities^[25].

Tanzania has also embraced integrated aqua-agriculture as a means to enhance food security and alleviate poverty. One notable approach is the integration of fish farming with paddy rice cultivation, particularly in the Kilombero Valley. Moreover, the integration of fish farming with livestock, such as ducks and chickens, has gained momentum in various regions, showcasing the versatility and adaptability of IAA practices.

Fish-Rice Integration

A notable IAA practice in Tanzania involves the integration of fish farming with rice cultivation. Particularly in areas like the Kilombero Valley where seasonal flooding of rice fields is managed to support fish culture during the wet season. This clever synergy enhances fish production and rice yields while capitalizing on the inherent benefits of both ecosystems.

Fish-Sugarcane plantation

Fish-Sugarcane integration has emerged as a sustainable and innovative agricultural practice among farmers in the Kagera region of Tanzania, particularly within sugarcane plantations. This integrated farming approach involves the simultaneous cultivation of sugarcane and the rearing of tilapia, creating a mutually beneficial relationship between the two. The sugarcane fields provide a conducive environment for fish farming, with their waterlogged conditions and interconnected irrigation channels serving as ideal fish habitats. This integrated system enhances resource utilization, boosts overall farm productivity (Fishpond water has high nutrient value thus used to fertilize sugarcane farm), and provides additional income streams for farmers. Furthermore, it promotes ecological balance and resilience in the face of changing environmental conditions. As a testament to the success of this practice, Fish-Sugarcane integration stands as a promising model for sustainable agriculture in the region, showcasing the potential for harmonizing diverse agricultural activities to achieve both economic and environmental benefits.

Livestock and Fish Integration

Tanzanian farmers have ingeniously merged livestock rearing, such as ducks or chickens, with fish farming. The shared water and nutrient resources in these integrated systems create a mutually beneficial relationship. Fish waste nourishes crops and pasture, while livestock waste contributes to nutrient enrichment in fishponds. Tanzania farmers have recognized the multifaceted benefits of this practice, as it not only maximizes land and water resource utilization but also contributes to diversified income streams. Livestock waste serves as a nutrient-rich fertilizer for fishponds, promoting the growth of aquatic organisms and improving water quality. Concurrently, fishponds provide an additional protein source for livestock feed, reducing dependency on external resources. This integrated system not only boosts productivity but also enhances the resilience of farming systems, particularly in regions vulnerable to climate variability. And this have been practiced in Mbeya Kiwira, where farmers integrate Tilapia, catfish with ducks and chicken.

Multi-Functional Ponds

Tanzania showcases the innovative use of multi-functional ponds, where fish farming coexists with other agricultural activities. The same pond that nurtures fish during one season can serve as a water reservoir for crop irrigation during another season, highlighting the adaptability and resource efficiency of IAA. This is proven in Rukwa, where local farmers utilize traditional earthen ponds for Tilapia and catfish integration. Fertilized by cow manure, the ponds also host yams along the dyke. To supplement commercial chicken feeds, they incorporate plant feeds like azola and yam leaves, driven by the lack of commercial feeds in the local area. The high protein content in azola benefits the fish, and the pond water is ingeniously employed for irrigating vegetables, creating a sustainable and interconnected farming system in this region.

Community-Based Initiatives

Community-led IAA initiatives have thrived in Tanzania, showcasing the power of local knowledge and collaboration. Farmers in various regions have collectively adopted IAA practices, underscoring the potential for grassroots movements to drive sustainable agricultural development. This have been evidenced in Mtwara, where farmers adopt a holistic approach to pond management, creating natural ponds with added dykes and surrounding them with strategically planted vegetation. Besides fostering a sustainable environment through beekeeping in nearby trees, the ponds are fertilized with cow manure. Milkfish thrive in this integrated system, as natural feeds such as algae are cultivated for the initial three months, supplemented later with additional feeds. Bees play a dual role, protecting both trees and ponds from potential theft. Moreover, the water from the pond serves a dual purpose, being used for vegetable irrigation, while the residue after honey harvest is ingeniously repurposed as

supplementary fish feed, showcasing an interconnected and environmentally conscious agricultural practices.

Challenges and Opportunities

While Tanzania's IAA practices exhibit great promise, challenges such as limited access to training, markets and infrastructure persist. Government support and capacity-building programs are crucial in overcoming these hurdles and scaling up IAA initiatives. The opportunities for cross-sector collaboration, research partnerships and innovative financing models offer a pathway to address these challenges effectively.

A study that aimed to analyse the potentials, challenges and opportunities for adopting IAA in Mvomero district of Morogoro region, Tanzania found that though there was a high level of awareness and interest in IAA among vegetable growers and fish farmers, only 14% of vegetable growers practised IAA compared to 75% of fish farmers. The lack of knowledge and quality inputs were the main challenges facing the IAA farming system. The study recommends practical training of vegetable farmers on IAA and Integrated Pest Management aspects as a means of promoting IAA^[21].

In conclusion, Tanzania's embrace of integrated aqua-agriculture reflects its commitment to sustainable development and resource management. Through the intricate interweaving of aquatic and agricultural ecosystems, Tanzania is crafting a narrative of resilience, innovation and prosperity. As IAA practices continue to evolve, Tanzania's journey serves as a testament to the transformative potential of harmonizing diverse elements to ensure food security, economic growth and ecological equilibrium.

1.3 TRENDS AND DIFFERENCES BETWEEN COUNTRIES

It is a common belief that specific policies must be prepared for integrated farming instead of highly intensive aquaculture systems. The conditions that exist in East Africa and Sub-Saharan Africa in total, are very difficult for intensive systems either due to infrastructure issues or to social-economical issues. By analysing their data, FAO estimated that 31% of Sub-Saharan land is suitable for small-scale integrated fish farming, which is equal to 9.2 million km²^[22]. By 2010, 0.5% of the land produced 35% of the total fish-production.

While Kenya, Uganda and Tanzania share a common goal of achieving food security and sustainable agricultural practices through integrated aqua-agriculture, they exhibit distinct trends and differences in their implementation approaches.

Kenya's focus on diversifying income sources through poultry or livestock integration stands out. Kenya has reached a point nowadays, where the trend of IAA is towards less labour-intensive technology. Moreover, the farmers are willing to invest time and money only if they can see that there is going to be profit with less risk and in a short time^[23]. Interviews with farmers showed that landowners are easier to be persuaded in integrating fish with crops or livestock, as long as they are trained and have some access to credit^[24]. The government however needs to gain access to more funds for these people^[11].

Uganda's integrated aqua-agriculture practises are focused on crops and fish. As the practices are mainly practised in remote villages, most data are not reported. However, all researchers agree that the farmers have little knowledge in IAA. They also advice that these farmers should form associations, which can help for their training and the extension services^[11]. The fact however, that there are efforts in integrating vermiculture and small-scale aquaculture systems highlight a localized and resource-efficient approach.

In Tanzania, tilapia and crops farming is the most common type of IAA as well^[25]. There seems to be a better training and informing of fish farmers for the advantages of these practices. For example, 73% of fish farmers are aware of IAA and 75% of them practice it. However, 81% of vegetable farmers are aware of IAA, but only 14% of them practice it. Training and better dissemination of the advantages should focus on these farmers. Although Tanzania is the 2nd largest rice producer in Sub-Saharan Africa, few farms practice the integration of fish in rice paddles^[25]. The country should therefore build on the example of Egypt for fish production in rice fields. It is promising however, that there is some research being carried out exclusively in IAA, and hopefully the challenges with water use and seed/feed of low quality, will be addressed. Farmers across Tanzania embrace integrated aqua-agriculture practices tailored to their regions. In Dodoma, earthen and concrete ponds support tilapia and catfish, utilizing natural feeds from plant leaves and addressing feed inadequacy. Kiwira-Mbeya implements a semi-intensive system for tilapia and catfish, optimizing market value with a mix of home-mixed and commercial feeds. Rukwa utilizes local earthen ponds fertilized with cow manure for tilapia and catfish, overcoming feed challenges through azola and yam leaves. Mtwara adopts natural ponds with dykes for milkfish, integrating beekeeping and vegetable plantation. Hombolo-Dodoma employs concrete ponds for tilapia, featuring cow manure fertilization and vegetable cultivation. In Mtwara, seawater and natural ponds host tilapia, combining natural feeds and homemade formulas. Karagwe-Kagera utilizes earthen ponds with cow manure fertilization for tilapia, integrated with sugarcane plantation, showcasing the versatility of integrated aqua-agriculture in addressing local challenges across Tanzania.

Furthermore, the variations in policy support, infrastructure development, and market access contribute to the unique trajectories of IAA practices in each country. Kenya's relatively more developed aquaculture sector and market networks have enabled certain advancements, while Uganda's grassroots-level adoption reflects community-driven initiatives. Tanzania's incorporation of IAA into broader rural development strategies showcases the integration's potential impact on poverty alleviation. The integration of vegetable cultivation, beekeeping, and strategic supplementation further exemplifies the holistic and sustainable nature of these farming systems, showcasing their potential to enhance food security and economic resilience across the country.

In conclusion, integrated aqua-agriculture is a dynamic and evolving practice that offers diverse benefits across the East African region. As Kenya, Uganda, and Tanzania continue to refine their approaches, the collective experiences and lessons learned from these countries will contribute to the ongoing development and optimization of integrated aqua-agriculture practices.

1.4 INTEGRATED AQUA-AGRICULTURE IN OTHER AFRICAN COUNTRIES

Integrated Agriculture in several other African countries is well established, particularly in countries where there is a history of fish farming such as South Africa, Egypt, and Nigeria.

1.4.1 Egypt

Integrated aquaculture and agriculture practices in the desert have shown a rapid increase the last 20 years. A large number of deserts landowners have established fish rearing facilities using water reservoirs as fish tanks. This proved successful and encouraging to integrate fish farming into their agriculture businesses. The Ministry of Agriculture supports this practice with several hundred of such farms expected to be operating within five years. Subsequently, a lot of privately-owned tilapia and carp hatcheries were established to supply with the needed amount of juveniles^[26].

Although a large part of Egypt is desert, yet Egypt has managed to become the largest rice producer in the Middle East and the African countries. Moreover the integration of rice and fish farming contributed to almost one third (32%) of the total aquaculture production of the country^[27]. Farmers there, have understood the rice-fish culture can become quite profitable in a short time. But the governments as well, have assisted this milestone. 20 million fingerlings are purchased by the Government from different hatcheries every year and distributed to rice farmers^[27]. This ensures a supply of animal protein to farmers as most of the harvested fish are consumed directly by them.

As water is valuable in these areas, tilapia is farmed with wheat on a rotary basis. When the conditions allow (from April to November) tilapia is farmed. However, as soon as temperature decreases (November or December) tilapia is harvested from ponds. In order not to leave ponds deserted until April (when they will be restocked), the farmers will cultivate wheat^[28]. Some projects were completed in a salty environment. In the RLR project (Rula for Land Reclamation), groundwater with a salinity of more than 26 g/L was utilized for European seabass (*Dicentrarchus labrax*) and gilthead seabream (*Sparus aurata*) farming. The water was then used for *Sarcocornia* planting. As electricity costs a lot and represents more than 30% of the total production cost, RLR is not operational yet^[21]. However, with the solar panels becoming more and more efficient, electricity cost can be reduced and make RLR operational again.

In recent years, Egypt has experienced a few failed attempts with aquaponics which has dampened excitement around the potential benefits. However, there is knowledge and interest in Egypt about integrated agriculture, and local demands for fresh fish and vegetables - in an environment where water can be scarce - indicates huge potential for growth^[29]. Experimental facilities using sandponics for instance, do not require separate mechanical and biological filters because the sand acts as both. Sand also provides a good growth medium for physical support for the plants, whilst allowing for good drainage, air circulation and root growth. Experimental systems with sandponics are suited to low-cost local production in Egypt where most crops rely on irrigation systems.

In general, the stakeholders in Egypt have reached a point, where the major problems of IAA are almost solved and the discussion is focused mainly on how to safeguard the sustainability of the sector: 'first fish, than crops' or the other way around^[30].

1.4.2 South Africa

A lot of IAA systems have been developed in South Africa over the last two decades and intensive studies were done, however not many people in the rural areas of the country know about the concept of aquaculture-agriculture systems^[31]. Other projects that were developed during the 80s and 90s, which cost a lot of money back then, have ceased to exist a lot of years ago. Mismanagement, inadequate planning and designs were all responsible for the unfortunate and yet foreseen cease of operation.

Non the less, the interest of people, researchers and investors for aquaculture remains high. For example, although vast areas of South Africa are covered from desert, projects for the integration of

fish with crops utilizing water pumped from rivers and dams even from 50 km away have been developed, indicating both the social importance and the economic potential^[28].

Under the principle of farming aquatic plants that can be used for feed and for filtering the effluent waters from fish tanks, aquaponic practices were developed globally. Aquaponics are well developed in South Africa as well, when compared to the other sub-Saharan countries. Aquaponics in the country has expanded in recent years in terms of the number of practitioners and the size of production systems, but is largely still characterized by a few operators, including demonstration and R&D systems at tertiary and government institutions, as well as small-scale backyard systems often run by schools, church or youth groups^[32]. Although most operations could be classified as subsistence (production suitable to feed a small number of individuals), there are a few medium-sized commercial operations, many driven by retired professionals seeking alternative income, as well as young graduates or entrepreneurs exploring new ventures. A 2016 survey estimated that between 60-100 functional aquaponics projects were spread across 9 provinces^[33], but these totals have likely increased since that time. The most commonly raised fish is tilapia (approximately 80%) in conjunction with leafy vegetables. Since most systems are small, aquaponics can be considered an emerging practice in South Africa alongside other types of integrated agriculture. One of the biggest challenges for aquaponics in South Africa is competition for markets from well-developed capture fisheries, a consumer preference for marine fish, as well as inexpensive field crops produced in conventional agriculture. Unlike in other parts of Africa where tilapia is prized, there are still negative connotations in South Africa associated with freshwater fish such as tilapia and catfish.

1.4.3 Nigeria

By 1995, 48% of all fish farms in Nigeria were practicing integrated agriculture with poultry, pigs, rabbits, sheep, goats, and cattle as well as with rice, plantains and bananas, fruit trees, vegetable crops, etc.^[34]. By then, poultry with fish was the most popular integration (50%). This was followed by sheep/goats/cattle at 38%, while pigs were integrated with 14% of the ponds surveyed. Rice farming was the least integrated practice with fish farming at only 1.6%^[34]. Since 1995, integration of fishponds with poultry and other livestock has become even more popular with rice-fish farming included. The Nigerian governments were very willing to use IAA to extend rice-fish farming throughout the country and increase both rice and fish production, increase water efficiency and add value to agricultural by-products used as nutrient inputs. The Nigerian Special Programme for Food Security (NSPFS) greatly encouraged the increased production^[34]. Most rice producers are small scale farmers with less than 0.5ha of land, producing less than 1tn of rice any given season. However, the average rice production is estimated at 2.1tn/ha/year. As the mechanical means of farming are scarce, labour-intensive farming

methods are used, making rice production more costly per hectare when comparing with neighbouring countries. Moreover, in lowland areas, farmers depend on annual flooding that is virtually impossible to control and does not allow for efficient use of fertilizer application or good fish husbandry. When the harvest period arrives, fish are captured for consumption or sales. The species which is mainly harvested in such conditions is catfish (*Clarias* or *Heterobranchus*), which has a substantial demand from consumers. Tilapia and other species sell for only 33% to 50% the amount of catfish. Sales from fish harvests in rice paddies contribute significantly to farmer's income: an additional 20% of the value of the rice to the farmer's revenues.

The major challenges of the IAA system in Nigeria are: ground water availability, unavailability of high quality fingerlings, availability of land, cooperative society, credit subsidies, input subsidies and access to information^[35]. Finally, a major problem is inadequate extension services, as the small scale farmers are lacking valuable information and training in fish husbandry and nobody to advise them, most of the time^[21].

West African countries such as Nigeria and Ghana, have seen strong growth in aquaculture production of freshwater fish, which has also translated into experimentation with aquaponics^[35]. In the case of Nigeria, for instance, aquaponics has developed as a food production method for urban areas, with an increasing number of small-scale operations near Lagos^[36, 37].

2 METHODOLOGY

To ensure a representative sample, a variety of IAA practices were purposefully selected from different regions of Kenya, Uganda and Tanzania. The selection was based mainly on the accessibility and availability of comprehensive data on integrated aqua-agricultural farmers. The study targeted farmers actively practicing integrated aqua-agricultural techniques within the selected countries. The databases from which the selection was done was unique for each country. In Kenya, for example, the participants were selected from the list of registered farmers obtained from the Department of Agriculture, Livestock, and Fisheries in each county. In Uganda, compilation of information in this review preceded a search of specific and multidisciplinary databases and academic publications with information on crop-livestock-fish integration. Under restricted measures, part of the raw data from earlier projects was analysed.

2.1 SURVEY DEVELOPMENT

The survey questionnaire was developed to capture information on various aspects of IAA (Survey detailed in Uganda's aquaculture production has continued to increase significantly, thus playing a key role in supplying animal protein sources for human consumption. However, majority of the farmers depend on earthen ponds for fish farming with few elements of integration. Other small-scale farmers depend on seasonal rain-fed crops namely; grain, vegetables and fruits. IAA has the potential to change the conventional agricultural practices in Uganda but achieving this will require improved extension services to provide knowledge and skills to the farmers. In addition, researchers need to investigate the best symbiotic combinations/associations and ratios of the aquatic animals/fish and the corresponding plants suited for the Uganda conditions, to achieve maximum yields of both. There is need to establish aquaponic training facilities for technological dissemination to off-takers (students and farmers). As the Uganda's population continues to increase and the threats of food insecurity intensifies, IAA represents a promising technology for producing both high-quality fish protein and crops.

Appendix A). The data collected was on sociodemographic, production, types and levels of integration, species of fish and other animals within the farms and the challenges faced by the farmers in their IAA practices. The survey tool was then digitized into Kobo Collect Tool for ease of administration. The tool was developed jointly by all the partners in T2.2.

2.2 KOBOCOLLECT TRAINING

After digitization of the tool, the enumerators and the partners of T2.2 were trained on how to use the KOBO tool for data collection in the field. The training of the partners was conducted by Maseno University while the enumerators were trained by the partners in the respective countries where the survey was done.

2.3 DATA COLLECTION

Data collection was done by the partners and enumerators mobilized and trained by the partners in the three countries. Data was collected through Smartphones after the questionnaire was accessed through the KOBO App installed on the phones. In some cases, the link to the questionnaire was sent to the farmers for self-administration based on agreement through a telephone conversation and consent. To establish the challenges affecting farmers in Uganda practicing IAA, focus group discussions were conducted. The focus group comprised of fish farmers, hatchery operators, traders, extension officers, and researchers. It was conducted in the West Nile and Central region of Uganda with a total of 56 and 41 participants, respectively (Table 1). During the local workshops, participants identified constraints to growth of the IAA.

TABLE 1. GENDER OF PARTICIPANTS IN THE FOCUS GROUP IN UGANDA

Group	Male	Female	Total
West Nile aquaculture group	43	13	56
Lake Albert Crescent aquaculture group	35	06	41

2.4 MAPPING

2.4.1 QGIS

The mapping of the facilities was performed using Quantum GIS (v3.24.2), deploying a data cleaned .csv file, to ensure consistency in the GPS location across facilities. The CRS (Coordinate Reference System) used was WGS84 EPSG:3857.

2.4.2 Interactive GeoMaps

Besides mapping in QGIS, another method to show all the entries gathered within this project was used; Interactive Geo Maps PRO (v1.6.8). This tool is a plug-in integrated into WordPress that creates markers with less detail than GIS on a specific map. In this case, PrAECTiCe-specific countries.

The information from the entries was used to consider the data protection of the farms involved in the survey. Only data regarding its activity is displayed, no detailed information such as name or address is provided.

The tooltip content is displayed using HTML language; a template was created. This kind of mapping will allow the public to navigate the map and see the different farm activities.

This plug-in also allows changes to or addition of more information using different display methods like images, icons or heat maps on the PrAECTiCe website.

2.5 DATA ANALYSIS

Analysis of the survey data was conducted using Microsoft Excel (Microsoft Corporation, 2021). Excel documents containing the survey results from each country were collated and cleaned to remove responses from non-operational farms, and those which either produced no fish, or only fish and no crops and livestock, these were not examples of IAA. Once cleaned and collated comparisons were made between countries on the various response categories. Where possible all three countries were compared however the data was not comparable in all cases and for Uganda a number of categories had no responses and could therefore not be compared to the other countries. A smaller number of categories were also not present within the Tanzania data and for these categories the analysis consisted simply of reporting the results from Kenya. Within Kenya, Kisumu region had the most complete set of data and in the case of some topics only these regions could be used when reporting survey responses. The low number of responses from Tanzania and the limited number of certain farm types restricted the potential for statistical analysis and therefore analysis was limited to reporting average figures for the various categories. The category of annual production had results reported in different formats (Tonnes, Kenyan shilling, number of fingerlings) and this meant it could unfortunately not be compared.

3 MAPS

As described in the methodology, maps were created in QGIS and displayed below. Interactive maps will also be available on the PrAectiCe website www.praectice.eu.

3.1 KENYA

155 IAA farms were identified and mapped in Kenya. 98 of these farms were located in the Kisumu region and 18 were located in the sub-county of Nyakach. No other region had more than 10 IAA farms identified. The spread of the farms identified may be due to the region that the data collection was based out of which was Kisumu.

FIGURE 4. QGIS MAP OF IAA PRACTICES IN KENYA.

3.2 UGANDA

In Uganda, 45 integrated aqua-agriculture farms were identified and mapped. Of these, 14 were located in the Western and Central regions, and 11 were located in the West-Nile region. No other region had more than 10 IAA farms identified.

FIGURE 5. QGIS MAP OF IAA PRACTICES IN UGANDA.

3.3 TANZANIA

19 farms practicing integrated aqua-agriculture were identified and mapped in Tanzania. 8 of these farms were located in the Morogoro region. The spread of the farms identified other than those in Morogoro were reached physically, so only a sample of fish farmers was reached.

FIGURE 6. QGIS MAP OF IAA PRACTICES IN TANZANIA.

4 RESULTS

In total data from a combined total of 210 farms was collected from Kenya, Tanzania, and Uganda (152 from Kenya, 13 from Tanzania, and 45 from Uganda). Of these farms a small number were non-operational or had no fish production recorded and they were removed from subsequent analysis, this left 141 farms in Kenya, 11 in Tanzania, and 41 in Uganda. Data from Uganda was restricted to only farm name and location and information on the species farmed. The results from Kenya had a limitation that a number of farms failed to include data on the education of owners, hours worked, income, or household size, with analysis of these variables conducted exclusively conducted on farms within the Kisumu region (one farm in Homabay/Rachuonyo North was also included), the 51 farms spread across the other 17 regions sampled are excluded from these particular comparisons.

4.1 OWNERSHIP AND MANAGEMENT

In Kenya and Tanzania farm ownership was split into eight different types; Community-based organizations, Faith based, Family, Government, Individual, Youth groups, Private, and Schools. Of the farms surveyed in Tanzania none fell under the school or youth group categories, but the remaining farms showed a fairly equal spread between categories (Figure 7). In Kenya almost 50 % of farms were individual owned with the next highest categories being Government, Family, and Private owned (Figure

7

), in Uganda 95% of the farms surveyed were individually owned.

FIGURE 7. PERCENTAGE SPLIT OF FARM TYPES WITHIN KENYA, TANZANIA AND UGANDA. (N= 141 KENYA, 11 TANZANIA, AND 41 UGANDA).

In Kenya respondents were typically older with over 43% being older than 56, and 65% being older than 46 (Figure 8). In Tanzania 63% of respondents were younger than 45, whilst in Uganda more than 50 % of farmers were aged 36 – 45, no farmers surveyed in Uganda were younger than 26 (Figure 8).

FIGURE 8. AGE OF RESPONDENTS IN KENYA, TANZANIA AND UGANDA (N= 141 IN KENYA, 11 IN TANZANIA, N=100 UGANDA).

In both Tanzania and Kenya men constituted the majority of respondents at 64% and 79% respectively (Figure 9). Household size was slightly larger in Kenya (n= 90) with a median of 6 people and 4 people in Tanzania.

FIGURE 9. GENDER DIVISION OF RESPONDENTS IN KENYA AND TANZANIA. (N= 141 KENYA, 11 TANZANIA).

The average education level of respondents was higher in Tanzania than in Kenya with over 45% of respondents possessing some form of postgraduate education (Figure 10). In Kenya respondents most typically had secondary (40%), tertiary (31%), or primary education (24%), with education above (4%) this being rare (Figure 10).

FIGURE 10. EDUCATION LEVEL OF RESPONDENTS IN KENYA AND TANZANIA. (N= 90 FOR KENYA, 11 FOR TANZANIA)

In the Kisumu region of Kenya data was also gathered on the degree or diploma subject for education at tertiary level and above. Teaching was the most common subject studied at higher level (Tertiary, undergraduate, postgraduate) by respondents, followed by agriculture, a range of other topics were present ranging from law to plumbing (Table 2).

TABLE 2. SUBJECT OF DIPLOMAS AND DEGREES AT TERTIARY, UNDERGRADUATE, AND POSTGRADUATE LEVELS FROM KENYAN RESPONDENTS (N=32)

Subject	Count
Education	12
Agriculture	6
Banking/finance/accountancy	3
Electrical/mechanical Engineering	2
Chemistry	1
Biology	1
Fisheries	1
Laboratory technology	1
Plumbing	1
Procurement	1
Counselling	1
ICT	1
Law	1

There was large variation in the number of workers in both Kenya and Tanzania but on average Tanzania had a larger mean 21 workers compared to 8 for Kenya. The smallest farms in each country were 2 workers in Tanzania and no additional workers in Kenya. The largest number employed in Tanzania was 60 workers and 46 in Kenya. Private organisations in both countries employed similar numbers of people on average (14 and 13 in Kenya and Tanzania respectively), however community-based and government organisation were much larger in Tanzania as were government lead farms (Figure 11). This increased the average number of workers.

FIGURE 11. AVERAGE NUMBER OF WORKERS IN KENYA AND TANZANIA BY FARM TYPE (N= 141 FOR KENYA AND 11 FOR TANZANIA).

4.2 INCOME, AND HOURS OF WORKS

Only six of the farms in Tanzania reported monthly income and therefore comparison between farm types was not possible. The average income of these farms was €156 a month (Average exchange rate August 2023) ranging from over €360 for two farms (one community based with 48 employees and one individual with 8 employees) to €36 for a faith-based and a family-based farm. A comparison could be made for the farms within the Kisumu region of Kenya (Figure 12), a caveat for this data is that the Faith, government, Youth-group, and Private categories only had 2, 1, 1, and 4 representatives respectively and therefore reliable averages were impossible to calculate. The highest monthly income reported was €511 whilst the lowest reported was €19. In Kenya, and Tanzania respondents worked similar amounts of time of the farm per day with an average of 6.2, 6.1 hours respectively (Figure 13). There was no relationship between hours worked per day and monthly income (Figure 14).

FIGURE 12. MONTHLY INCOME BY FARM TYPE IN KENYA. (N=90)

FIGURE 13. AVERAGE DAILY HOURS WORKED ON THE FARM IN KENYA AND TANZANIA. (N= 90 FOR KENYA AND 9 FOR TANZANIA)

FIGURE 14. AVERAGE MONTHLY INCOME AND DAILY HOURS WORKED FOR FARMS IN KENYA AND TANZANIA. (N=90 FOR KENYA AND 6 FOR TANZANIA)

The farms in the Kisumu region of Kenya reported average annual production capacity in Kenyan shillings. These values were then converted to Euro based on the average conversion rate for August 2023. The average annual income for these farms (n=90) was €1,265. There was no correlation between time in operation and annual income, there was also no correlation between number of employees and annual income. Unlike the monthly income records, private farms (n=4) reported the highest annual production capacity at €3,174, this was followed by the one youth-group farm in the region Figure 15. Individual farms (n=73) reported an average annual production capacity of €1,327. Family farms (n=10) were more than half this value at €508.

FIGURE 15. ANNUAL PRODUCTION CAPACITY IN EUROS FARM TYPE IN KENYA. (N=90)

4.3 PRODUCTION

4.3.1 Aquaculture

Data on the type of production was available for all farms in Kenya, Tanzania, and Uganda. In the three countries, aquaculture is used to produce eight different species (Ornamentals are classified as one species), the popularity of each species can be seen in Figure 16. The most popular species to farm is Tilapia, grown in over 98% of farms in Kenya and Uganda, and 90% of farms in Tanzania. This is mainly due to the high levels of acceptability of Tilapia cross cultures compared to catfish that has some cultural and religious restrictions. Catfish is the next most common aquaculture species being farmed in 33, 55, and 15% of farms in Kenya, Tanzania, and Uganda respectively. This trend has been observed in many countries since catfish is a hardy fish that tolerates poor culture conditions and has a high meat to bone ratio. One farm of the 11 surveyed in Tanzania produces Mwatiko (Milk fish), whilst another produces sea cucumber. This can be explained by the fact that mariculture is not well developed in Kenya and Tanzania while Uganda is land-locked. Two farms out of 41 farms in Uganda produce Mirror Carp. Two farms out of 141 in Kenya produce goldfish, Three produce Labeo, whilst another four produced ornamental fish. These species are illustrated in Figure 17.

FIGURE 16. AQUACULTURE SPECIES GROWN IN THE FARMS SURVEYED AND THEIR FREQUENCY. THE TOTAL PERCENTAGE FOR EACH COUNTRY IS MORE THAN 100 % AS SOME FARMS GROW MORE THAN ONE SPECIES. (N= 141, 11, AND 41 FOR KENYA, TANZANIA, AND UGANDA RESPECTIVELY).

FIGURE 17. PICTURES OF THE MAIN AQUACULTURED SPECIES PRODUCED ON THE FARMS STUDIED. FROM LEFT TO RIGHT AND TOP TO BOTTOM THE SPECIES ARE TILAPIA, CATFISH, MIRROR CARP, MWATIKO (MILKFISH), SEA CUCUMBER, AND GOLDFISH/ORNAMENTALS.

A large number of farms grow more than one species of fish. In Uganda monoculture of only one aquaculture species is the most common at 85% of farms but 12% of farms grow two species and one farm grows three species. Monoculture is also the most common form of aquaculture production in Kenya seen in 68% of farms, 27% grow two species, 4% grow three, and two farm produced four different aquaculture species (Tilapia, Catfish, Labeo, and goldfish). In Tanzania dual culture is the most common (64%), typically this are tilapia and catfish, the rest is monoculture of tilapia. Polyculture,

especially of tilapia and catfish, is prominent in many parts of Africa since catfish is used to control the population of tilapia in these facilities.

FIGURE 18. NUMBER OF AQUACULTURE SPECIES PER FARM IN KENYA, TANZANIA, AND UGANDA. (N= 141, 11, AND 41 FOR KENYA, TANZANIA, AND UGANDA RESPECTIVELY).

4.3.2 Crops

The majority of farms grow crops as well as aquaculture species, of these farms vegetables are the most popular crop of choice. In Kenya 87% of farms grow crops and 87 % of the total number of farms grow vegetables, and 16% grew fruit. In Tanzania, 91% of farms grow vegetables and 18% grow seaweed. In Uganda 46% grow crops as well as aquaculture products with 44% growing vegetables and 2% growing rice. For the Kisumu region of Kenya extensive information was collected on the types of fruits and vegetables farmed, 34% of farms in these regions reported farming only one species of crop, 38% of farms in this region grow three of more crops alongside their aquaculture production (Figure 19). The species grown in these regions can be seen in Table 3. The integration of crops with fish production is common in many parts of Kenya with the water from the culture facilities being used to irrigate crops with the most common being vegetables.

FIGURE 19. NUMBER OF CROPS GROWN PER FARM IN THE KISUMU AND NYAKACH REGIONS OF KENYA. (N=90).

TABLE 3. CROP SPECIES GROWN IN THE KISUMU AND NYAKACH REGIONS OF KENYA AND THEIR POPULARITY. (N=90).

	Crop	Percentage of farms	
	Vegetables	93%	
	Cereals	20%	
	Fruit	19%	
	Sugarcane	14%	
	Banana	13%	
	Maize	9%	
	Forrest	9%	
	Mango	9%	
	Orange	9%	
	Rice	8%	
	Seaweed	6%	
	Paw Paw	6%	
	Cassava	4%	
	Beans	3%	
	Avocado	3%	
	Potatoes	2%	
	Other Cash crops	1%	
	Sweet potatoes	1%	
	Arrow	1%	
	Tomatoes	1%	
	Guava	1%	
	Mushroom	1%	
	Yam	1%	
	Alma	1%	

4.3.3 Livestock and other animals

Almost 75% of farms surveyed produced livestock or other animals alongside their aquaculture species. In Kenya production of livestock or animals was more common with over 75% of farms producing chickens and 62% producing cattle, this compared to 27% for both species in Tanzania and 22% and

34% respectively in Uganda. Integration of fish and chicken is the most common form of IAA in Kenya and has been seen to lead to high yields of both.

FIGURE 20. PERCENTAGE OF FARMS PRODUCING CHICKENS, CATTLE, OR OTHER LIVESTOCK IN KENYA, TANZANIA, OR UGANDA. (N= 141, 11, AND 41 FOR KENYA, TANZANIA, AND UGANDA RESPECTIVELY).

In Kenya, 23% of farms produce livestock or animals other than chickens or cattle, these species and their popularity can be seen in Table 4.

TABLE 4. LIVESTOCK SPECIES FARMED IN KENYA AND THE FREQUENCY AMONG THE FARMS SURVEYED. (N= 141)

Animal	Percentage of farms
Chicken	72%
Cattle	57%
Bees	16%
Duck	3%
Turkey	3%
Pig	3%
Black Solider Fly	3%
Worms	2%
Geese	1%

The majority of farms focusing on livestock in Tanzania (45%), and all the farms in Uganda, had a monoculture (Figure 21). Farming two species of animal (beside aquaculture species) is the predominant choice for farms in Kenya (52%). Two farms in Kenya produce five species of livestock or animals alongside aquaculture operations, both farms produce chickens, ducks, turkeys, pigs, and black soldier fly.

FIGURE 21. NUMBER OF AQUACULTURE SPECIES PER FARM IN KENYA, TANZANIA, AND UGANDA. (N= 141, 11, AND 41 FOR KENYA, TANZANIA, AND UGANDA RESPECTIVELY).

4.3.4 Integrated aquaculture-agriculture systems

As mentioned above, whilst all farms included in the analysis perform some form of integrated aquaculture-agriculture (IAA), not all farms incorporated both crops and livestock/animals. In Kenya and Tanzania farming all three types of products was the most common system at 76% and 55% of farms respectively. The next most common form of IAA in these countries is aquaculture and crops. In Uganda the most common form of IAA is the integration of aquaculture with livestock, followed by aquaculture and crops, only 2% of farms in Uganda has aquaculture, crops, and livestock.

FIGURE 22. TYPES OF INTEGRATED AQUACULTURE-AGRICULTURE SYSTEMS EMPLOYED AND THEIR FREQUENCY IN KENYA, TANZANIA, AND UGANDA. (N= 141, 11, AND 41 FOR KENYA, TANZANIA, AND UGANDA RESPECTIVELY).

4.4 CHALLENGES AND RECOMMENDATIONS

4.4.1 Kenya and Tanzania

Data was collected from farms in Kenya, Tanzania, and Uganda on the biggest challenges each farm faces. Data for Uganda was collected through focus group discussion whilst data from Kenya and Tanzania was collected as part of the surveys and is discussed further down. In Kenya and Tanzania 21 key challenges were identified from farmer responses:

- Inadequate quality feeds and seeds
- Fish handling and storage facilities
- Market access
- Fluctuating Market prices
- Inadequate production units
- Lack of skilled personnel
- Drought

- Consumer perceptions on farmed fish
- Limited extension services
- Unfavourable policies
- Predators
- Flood
- Security/theft
- Availability of water
- Access to capital
- Other input costs
- Fish diseases
- Electricity
- Pests/ diseases for crops and livestock
- Availability of feed
- Price of seeds

The greatest challenge that farmers face in both countries is inadequate quality of feeds and seeds, this issue was highlighted in 91% of Tanzanian farms and 81% of Kenyan farms. This is mainly because most of the fish feeds used in Kenya is imported making them expensive for fish farmers. The second most common issue is market access in Kenya and access to good fish handling and storage facilities in Tanzania (3rd most important issue in Kenya). The next most important issues between both countries are lack of skilled personnel, inadequate production units, limited extension services, fluctuating market prices, and drought.

FIGURE 23. BIGGEST CHALLENGES FACED BY FARMERS AND THE PERCENTAGE OF FARMS LISTING EACH ISSUE IN KENYA, AND TANZANIA. (N= 141, 11, FOR KENYA, AND TANZANIA RESPECTIVELY).

In Kenya and Tanzania information was collected on respondents' recommendations for successful management of the farm. Responses to this question "Recommendations for successful management of the farm?" were often similar to responses to the question "Key Management Challenges?" in that they focused on deficiencies or struggles that the farms faced and provided a recommendation on what was most needed to help the farm succeed (Figure 24). The most common recommendations were to provide training to farmers and managers and to increase funding to farmers. Providing access to quality feed and seed, market access, and capacity building and extension services were also seen as important recommendations on how to improve farm management. As with the main challenges the provision of water, prevention of predators was also mentioned by a number of respondents, in both Tanzania and Kenya 9% of respondents mentioned the need or desire to expand production. Many farmers talked about the need for collaboration with other parties, either through training from the university, taking on students, partnerships with other companies or knowledge exchanges.

FIGURE 24. MAIN RECOMENDATIONS FOR SUCCESSFUL FARM MANAGEMENT IN KENYA AND TANZANIA (N= 141 FOR KENYA AND 11 FOR TANZANIA)

A small number of respondents answered the question with advice and general recommendations to other current or potential farmers. This advice included the need for farmers to be ready and prepared before starting farming, to have dedication, to have passion and commitment. One respondent stated that “Integrated aqua-agriculture” is the best project, that if invest your time and sprit then you're sure to succeed”, however two respondents raised concerns about being interviewed by various organizations but without receiving assistance from them.

4.4.2 Uganda

Through group discussions with key farmers in Uganda, the top five challenges were recorded and are listed in Table 5. The limited amount of expertise undermines diffusion and adoption of IAA technologies especially aquaponic farming in many parts of the country. Most small-scale farmers practicing IAA lack the technical capabilities to manage both the fish and crops with regards to proper design of systems, disease control, and maintenance of nutrient balance which greatly affects productivity. Due to limited knowledge, farmers end up designing systems that are not very efficient which lowers total factor productivity. In many parts of the rural areas, power supply is unreliable, which affects the productivity of aquaponic systems, and even in those areas where power is reliable, the cost is too high to be afforded by farmers. Renewable energy sources (for example solar energy) need to be integrated into an aquaponic system for a sustainable constant power supply.

TABLE 5. MAIN CHALLENGES BY FARMERS PRACTISING IAA IN UGANDA (DATA COLLECTED BY FOCUS GROUP).

Challenges	Rank
Limited knowledge and skills to manage both fish and crops/livestock	1
Unreliable power supply	2
Expensive feeds	3
Lack niche market for aquaculture products	4
Water challenges in terms of quality and quantity	5

5 CONCLUSION

5.1 KENYA

The results showed that Kenya has embraced IAA practices with different types and levels of integration of fish, crops and livestock. Some of the challenges identified include high cost of quality feeds and seeds, access to market, post-harvest handling and access to finance. To address these challenges and tap into the opportunities identified, it will be important to strengthen the sector through policies, capacity building, enhanced access to credit and markets and strong support for post-harvest handling and processing. Despite the challenges, IAA has high potential in improving food production and enhancing food and nutrition security in Kenya while providing employment to the youth and women.

5.2 TANZANIA

The investigation of IAA systems underscores this country's pivotal role in addressing the pressing global need for sustainable, high-yield food production in Tanzania. As the challenge of an exponentially growing population is confronted, the demand for resource-efficient practices becomes paramount. The alarming statistics of water usage in Tanzanian agriculture, especially in dryland regions, necessitate a paradigm shift towards sustainable farming techniques. The "more crops per drop" intensification approach, strategically integrated with aquaculture, emerges as a transformative solution to optimize water usage and bolster yields in water-scarce regions.

The synergy between aquaculture and agriculture within IAA stands as a beacon for environmentally conscious farming in Tanzania. By transforming aquaculture into a non-consumptive production sector, IAA not only enhances farm productivity but also addresses the issues of water quality in fishponds and mitigates the environmental impact of nutrient-rich water discharge. The reduction in water-related expenses and the decreased reliance on chemical fertilizers further underscore the economic and ecological benefits of IAA in Tanzanian. The PrAECTiCe project's mapping of IAA practices in Tanzania provided valuable insights into the integration methods, species selection, and associated challenges specific to this East African country.

5.3 UGANDA

Uganda's aquaculture production has continued to increase significantly, thus playing a key role in supplying animal protein sources for human consumption. However, majority of the farmers depend on earthen ponds for fish farming with few elements of integration. Other small-scale farmers depend on seasonal rain-fed crops namely; grain, vegetables and fruits. IAA has the potential to change the conventional agricultural practices in Uganda but achieving this will require improved extension services to provide knowledge and skills to the farmers. In addition, researchers need to investigate the best symbiotic combinations/associations and ratios of the aquatic animals/fish and the corresponding plants suited for the Uganda conditions, to achieve maximum yields of both. There is need to establish aquaponic training facilities for technological dissemination to off-takers (students and farmers). As the Uganda's population continues to increase and the threats of food insecurity intensifies, IAA represents a promising technology for producing both high-quality fish protein and crops.

6 APPENDIX A

QUESTIONNAIRE

General Details

- Country
- County/District
- Name of Farm
- GPS Coordinates of Farm

Sociodemographic Characteristics

- Category of Respondent
- Gender
- Age
- Education Level
- Marital Status
- Household Size
- How many hours a day do you spend working on the farm?
- Average Monthly Income

Farm Operations

- Status of Farm – Operational/Dormant
- How Many Years in Operation?
- If Dormant – Why?
- How long has it been dormant?
- Type of Organization/ownership of the farm?
 - Individual
 - Family
 - Government
 - Private
 - Community-based organisation
 - Faith-based organisation
 - Youth group
 - Women group
 - Other
- How many people are employed on the farm?
- How many are:
 - Men
 - Women
 - Youth

- Vulnerable/marginal group

Production

- Which species of fish do you culture?
 - Tilapia
 - Catfish
 - Labeo
 - Protopterus
 - Other
- What modes of integration in the farm?
 - Vegetables
 - Rice
 - Chicken
 - Livestock
 - Black soldier fly
 - Seaweeds
 - Crabs
 - Artemia
 - Other
- Estimated annual production capacity?
- Key Management Challenges?
 - Inadequate quality feeds and seeds
 - Unfavourable policies
 - Lack of skilled personnel
 - Fish Diseases
 - Market Access
 - Fish handling and storage facilities
 - Fluctuating market prices
 - Consumer perceptions on farmed fish
 - Limited extension services
 - Inadequate production units
 - Drought
 - Other
- Recommendations for successful management of the farm?
- Any comments?

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